

Extend Access, Expand the Community, and Exemplify Good Practices for CI through
Science Gateways

Integrating OpenTopography API into Design Safe Recon Portal for Enhanced Geospatial Data Analysis

- **Web and Mobile Applications team at TACC**

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- **Manager:** *Tracy Brown*

Goal: *Collaborating to enhance the Design Safe Recon Portal's capabilities & Dedicated to advancing natural hazard research*

Exploring the integration of topographic data, including LIDAR point clouds and Digital Elevation Models, sourced from the OpenTopography API to enhance the portal's capabilities, providing a more comprehensive understanding of natural hazard events and their impacts.

Recon Portal Enhancements

- **OpenTopography Integration:** High-resolution topographic data for detailed spatial analysis and modeling
 - Center points data: Availability of topography data indicated on the world map
 - Multi polygons data: Detailed boundary definitions of geospatial areas
- **UI Enhancements:** Intuitive and visually informative map interface with color-coded event markers
- **Advanced Filtering:** Precise search refinement options for OpenTopography data
 - Author, title, keyword, description, location search, and date ranges
- **Secure File Retrieval:** Tapis-enabled secure file fetching for data integrity and privacy
- **Modernized Web Portal:** Upgraded application framework for improved performance, scalability, and maintainability
 - Faster rendering and more responsive interactions
 - Efficient and modular codebase for developer